

Automatic Line Art Extraction and Line Correction System from Original Images Based on Image Processing Algorithms for AI Animation Production

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Abstract

In AI comics and AI animation production pipelines, extracting line art from colored original images and correcting their quality is an essential but labor-intensive process. This paper proposes a two-phase pipeline consisting of line art extraction through ΔE -based boundary detection in Lab color space and DFS track construction (Phase 1), and line correction through brush-based region selection and region filling (Phase 2). In Phase 1, the Dark-side Bias strategy of calculating color distance between adjacent pixels and selecting darker pixels ensures consistent line thickness. In Phase 2, morphological refinement and image restoration techniques are applied only to user-selected areas, and distance transform-based alpha masks generate smooth boundaries. This system provides a lightweight solution suitable for web-based real-time editing environments, operating without training data.

1. Introduction

In comics, webtoons, and animation production, line art is a key element that defines the structure of characters and backgrounds. In traditional production workflows, artists either manually draw separate line art layers on top of colored original images or perform post-processing to separate lines from completed color images. This process requires considerable time and labor, and is a major cause of bottlenecks, especially in animation production where large numbers of frames must be processed[4].

With recent advances in deep learning technology, GAN and CNN-based line art extraction methods have been proposed[1][2]. These methods show excellent performance in extracting consistent line art from original images of various styles. However, practical limitations exist, including the need for large-scale training dataset construction, GPU-based inference environments, and retraining requirements for new styles. Particularly when real-time responsiveness is required in web-based editing tools, inference delays from deep learning models become a factor that degrades user experience.

Meanwhile, quality correction of extracted line art is also an important challenge. Anti-aliasing residues, discontinuous line segments, and unintended noise directly affect the quality of subsequent work (colorization, animation)[6]. Most existing methods process the entire image in batch, making it difficult to selectively correct only specific areas.

This paper proposes a two-phase pipeline to solve these problems. In Phase 1, structurally consistent line art is extracted without training data through ΔE -based boundary detection in Lab color space and DFS track construction. In Phase 2, users can non-destructively correct only the parts they want through brush-based region selection and image restoration techniques. The proposed system simultaneously achieves three goals: lightweight operation, real-time performance, and interactive editing support.

2. Related Work

Deep Learning-based Line Art Extraction

Yoo and Yang[1] proposed a method to automatically extract geometric line drawings from 2D cartoon original images of various production techniques using GAN. This method overcomes style diversity and generates consistent line art, but requires training data construction and GPU inference environments. Xin et al.[2] proposed Progressive Full Data CNN to extract line art from anime-style completed images, emphasizing industrialization efficiency. Their method addresses the limitations of traditional filters such as Sobel, Laplace, and Canny that cannot output good results and require manual parameter adjustments.

Traditional Edge Detection Methods

Zhang et al.[7] proposed a method to simultaneously extract decorative lines and edges from cartoon images using Hessian matrix and Gaussian derivative. They use non-maximum suppression on the image's second derivative of Gaussian to locate possible decorative line centers, then verify existence through directional zero-crossing. Such traditional methods have high computational efficiency but are vulnerable to noise in images with complex color distributions or anti-aliasing. This study overcomes these limitations by combining color distance (ΔE) in Lab color space with track-based connection.

Line Art Colorization and Quality Correction

Lee and Lee[3] proposed a two-stage generator for automatic colorization of anime style illustrations using GAN-based image-to-image colorization with color point hinting. Kim[4] studied the creative use of AI for efficiency improvement of labor-intensive line drawing work in comics production, highlighting the practical need for automated line art processing. Lee and Lee[6] presented a service platform for serving line-art automatic colorization models, demonstrating the industrial applicability of such systems.

Region-wise Correspondence in Line Art

Li et al.[5] introduced a Transformer-based framework for predicting region-wise correspondence between manga line art images without annotations. Their method uses edge-aware clustering and region matching to establish coherent region-level correspondences, achieving 78.4-84.4% region-level accuracy. This approach provides theoretical grounding for Phase 2's morphological post-processing and region selection methodology.

3. Proposed Method

System Overview

The proposed system consists of two independent Phases. Phase 1 is the stage of extracting line art from colored original images, and Phase 2 is the stage of correcting the line quality of areas selected by the user with a brush. The two Phases are executed sequentially, and the output of Phase 1 is used as input to Phase 2.

Phase 1: Line Art Extraction

Phase 1 consists of four stages: preprocessing, candidate detection, track construction, and rasterization. Figure 1 visually shows the processing results of each stage.

Figure 1. Phase 1 Line Art Extraction Process. (a) **Preprocessing:** L channel quantization and blur applied after conversion from RGB to Lab color space. (b) **Candidate Detection:** ΔE -based boundary detection result, marking areas where color distance between adjacent pixels exceeds the threshold. (c) **Track Construction:** Candidate pixels connected by DFS are grouped into tracks, visualized by overlaying detected lines on the original image. (d) **Output:** Final binary line art mask.

Preprocessing: The input RGB image is converted to Lab color space. Lab color space is robust to lighting changes because brightness (L) and color (a, b) are separated. Quantization is applied to the L channel to group subtle brightness changes, and Gaussian blur simplifies anti-aliasing boundaries.

Candidate Detection: The color distance ΔE to adjacent pixels is calculated at each pixel. ΔE is defined as the Euclidean distance in Lab space.

$$\Delta E = \sqrt{((L_1 - L_2)^2 + (a_1 - a_2)^2 + (b_1 - b_2)^2)}$$

If ΔE is above the threshold, it is judged as a boundary, and only the darker pixel (lower L value) of the two boundary pixels is selected as a candidate. This Dark-side Bias strategy utilizes domain knowledge that lines in comics are generally darker than their surroundings. Pixels brighter than the brightness threshold are excluded as non-lines.

Track Construction: Candidate pixels are connected by DFS (Depth-First Search) to construct tracks. Adjacent candidate pixels are grouped into one track, and tracks shorter than the minimum length are removed as noise. Single-pixel noise is automatically filtered at this stage.

Rasterization: The constructed tracks are converted to a binary mask. Line thickness can be adjusted according to parameters.

Phase 2: Line Correction

Phase 2 consists of five stages: correction region determination, mask refinement, region filling, alpha mask generation, and patch extraction. Figure 2 shows the overall workflow of brush-based line correction.

Figure 2. Phase 2 Line Correction Process. (a) **Original Image:** Colored original image with line art extracted in Phase 1. (b) **Brush Selection of Area to Correct:** User designates line area requiring correction with brush tool (red area). (c) **Correction Layer Patch:** Result of morphological refinement and region filling applied to selected area, patch including distance transform-based alpha mask. (d) **Line Correction Applied:** Final result with patch naturally composited to original image through alpha blending.

Correction Region Determination: The intersection of line pixels extracted in Phase 1 and the area selected by the user with a brush is calculated. The area is expanded by a margin to include anti-aliasing residues, but is limited not to exceed the brush area boundary.

Mask Refinement: Morphological closing operation fills small holes, and opening operation removes small protrusions. This generates a continuous mask that allows region filling to work more naturally.

Region Filling: Image restoration (inpainting) techniques are used to fill the mask area with surrounding pixel colors. The restoration radius is determined proportionally to parameters.

Alpha Mask Generation: Distance transform is applied to calculate how far each pixel is from the boundary. The center has high alpha values and edges have low alpha values to generate smooth boundaries. The feathering radius controls the external attenuation range, and additional Gaussian blur is applied if needed.

Patch Extraction: The bounding box of the area with alpha values is calculated and only that area is cropped. The return values consist of the corrected partial image, blending alpha mask, and origin coordinates.

4. Discussion

Advantages of the Proposed Method

The proposed two-phase pipeline offers several practical advantages over existing approaches. First, the Lab ΔE -based boundary detection operates without requiring training data or GPU resources, making it immediately deployable in resource-constrained environments such as web-based editing tools. Unlike deep learning methods that require extensive dataset preparation and model training for each new art style[1][2], our method generalizes across different illustration styles through parameter adjustment alone.

Second, the Dark-side Bias strategy addresses a fundamental characteristic of comic and animation line art. By consistently selecting darker pixels at color boundaries, the method produces lines with uniform thickness regardless of the surrounding color distribution. This domain-specific insight eliminates the double-line artifacts commonly observed in traditional edge detection methods[7].

Third, the brush-based interactive correction in Phase 2 enables non-destructive editing workflows. Artists can selectively refine specific regions without affecting the rest of the image, which aligns with professional production practices where iterative refinement is essential. The patch-based return structure further enhances efficiency by minimizing data transfer between server and client.

Limitations and Challenges

Despite these advantages, the proposed method has notable limitations. The ΔE threshold and other parameters require manual tuning for optimal results across different image characteristics. Images with low contrast between lines and surrounding colors may produce incomplete line extraction, as the color distance may fall below the detection threshold.

The track-based noise filtering, while effective for removing isolated pixels, may inadvertently eliminate intentional short strokes or fine details that artists deliberately include. Finding the optimal minimum track length requires balancing noise removal against detail preservation.

For Phase 2, the inpainting-based region filling assumes that surrounding pixels provide appropriate color information for reconstruction. In cases where lines border regions with significantly different colors on each side, the filled result may exhibit color bleeding or unnatural transitions.

Comparison with Deep Learning Approaches

Deep learning-based methods[1][2] demonstrate superior performance in handling complex artistic styles and producing semantically meaningful line extraction. However, they require substantial computational resources and training data preparation. The proposed method trades some extraction quality for significant gains in deployment simplicity and processing speed.

A hybrid approach combining our lightweight extraction with deep learning-based refinement could potentially leverage the strengths of both paradigms. The proposed method could serve as a fast initial extraction, with selective deep learning enhancement applied only to challenging regions identified through confidence metrics.

Potential Applications

Beyond standalone line art extraction, the proposed pipeline has potential applications in several domains. In webtoon-to-animation conversion workflows, rapid line extraction enables efficient keyframe preparation. The interactive correction capability supports quality control processes where human oversight remains essential.

The modular two-phase architecture also facilitates integration with existing production tools. Phase 1 can operate as a preprocessing step for automatic colorization systems[3][6], while Phase 2 provides manual refinement capabilities that complement automated processes.

Future Directions

Several research directions merit further investigation. Adaptive parameter estimation based on image statistics could reduce manual tuning requirements. Multi-scale track construction would better accommodate varying line thicknesses within single images. Integration with region correspondence methods[5] could enable consistent line extraction across animation sequences.

Additionally, comprehensive quantitative evaluation against established benchmarks would strengthen validation of the proposed approach. User studies with professional artists would provide valuable insights into practical workflow integration and usability improvements.

5. Conclusion

This paper proposed a two-phase pipeline for extracting line art from colored original images and correcting quality. Phase 1's Lab ΔE -based boundary detection and DFS track construction presents a methodology that can extract structurally consistent line art without training data. The Dark-side Bias strategy is an effective approach for ensuring line thickness consistency, utilizing domain characteristics of comic line art. Phase 2's brush-based interactive correction system has high practical utility as users can selectively process only desired areas. Distance transform-based alpha masks enable natural blending without staircase artifacts at boundaries.

The proposed method is a lightweight structure that operates without training data and GPU resources, suitable for web-based real-time editing environments. The patch-based data transmission structure minimizes network load to improve responsiveness.

Future research plans include automatic optimization through adaptive parameter estimation, support for various line thicknesses through multi-scale track construction, and hybrid approaches with deep learning-based methods. We also plan to conduct systematic experiments according to the proposed evaluation framework and study integrated utilization methods in webtoon-to-animation conversion pipelines.

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